

A Study on the relationship between ‘Awareness’ and ‘Implementation’ of Green HRM in Mining industry in West Bengal

Swarnalata Basak

Research Scholar

Department of Business Administration (Human Resource)

The University of Burdwan, West Bengal, India

Email: basakswarnalata2019@gmail.com

Dr. Abhishek Mishra

Assistant Professor

Department of Business Administration (Human Resource)

The University of Burdwan, West Bengal, India

Email: amishra@mbahr.buruniv.ac.in

Abstract:

The environmental catastrophe resulting to global warming and diminishing supply of natural non-renewable resources, has forced as many organizations across the world to prioritize environmental management programs to achieve sustainable targets with an objective to remain operational in the upcoming future. To meet this end, the organizations have started to incorporate environmental protection policies to guide their business operations. Green HRM is one of the emerging initiatives in the direction of sustainability adopted by the business organizations. Green HR incorporates with human resource activities which are in eco-friendly and promoting uses of resources sustainably within the organization. However, to make any organization green, it becomes an imperative to make the employees aware towards the Green HRM resulting in conversion of employees into environmental friendly employees. This paper explores the awareness of employees towards Green HRM and examines the extent to which the Green HRM practices are implemented in the mining industry, particularly the mining PSUs in West Bengal. A questionnaire was distributed among different employees of selected PSU. The collected data was statistically evaluated by using "SPSS" 3.0. Finally, this paper also tries to focus on the relationship between employee awareness towards Green HRM and the implementation of Green HRM practices in the mining sector in West Bengal. The results indicate about positive relationship between the two factors. It recommends to increasing awareness of HR employees towards green will transforming normal HR to a Green HR employee in future.

Keywords: Green Human resource management, Green Employees, Public Sector Undertakings, Green Human Resource Management practices.

Introduction

With the rapid industrial growth accompanied by latest advancements in technology, has changed the very way we live in contemporary times. While rapid industrialization has been incessantly catering to fulfill the insatiable needs of the human civilization, the uncontrolled exploitation of natural resources is depleting the resources in unimaginable ways. This uncontrolled taming of natural resources has causing significant damages to human life and the environment in form of floods, landslides, industrial smog etc. Eventually, the business organizations have started taking note of the graveness of the environmental concerns and slowly but gradually started to address the issue through several green initiative. In management parlance, 'Green' refers to eco-friendly or environmental practices being undertaken by the business organizations. Also called 'green activities', these initiatives direct an organization to diminish its negative impact on the environment and protect the natural resources (Ramus, 2002). It includes reduction of waste, decrease in consumption of hazardous material friendly, ISO 14001 certification adopted by a company for effective environmental management thus to protect the environment of a company (Azevedo et al., 2011, Arocena et al, 2021). The 'Go Green' strategy is a step forward towards integrating environmental concerns into management principles and practices. Organizations must therefore comprehend, motivate, and enable the intellectual capital to implement practices on green management in the workplace (Goswami and Ranjan, 2015).

In the industrial sector, 'Green' the term that describes about the preservation and conservation of natural resources which minimize or avoid the environmental pollution (Opatha and Arulrajah, 2014). People need to be kept aware of the necessity of being environmentally conscious in order to protect the environment, utilize natural resources as efficiently as possible, establish a natural environment, and avoid causing pollution. Organizations serve as a part of our society and thus have some concern and responsibility towards people and environment including survival of future generation.

Governments across nations have set up new policies relating to environmental protection and organizations are mandated to adopt the set policy guidelines to maintain sustainability. In their attempt to address the emerging environmental concerns, the organizations are meticulously integrating the "go green" concept into their business operations (Raza and Khan, 2022). The

organizations are ensuring that the people policies are aligned with environmental policies for better management of people, planet and profit. By embracing and implementing the Green HRM Practices, organization can support their workforce to create an environmental conscious culture that will affect and reflect their commitment, behavior, attitudes, and performance towards sustainability (Ansari et al., 2021). Implementing green policies and encouraging eco-friendly activities among staff members can strengthen an organization's commitment to sustainability, which will ultimately result to lower consumption of resources, lower carbon emissions, and an overall improvement in the management of the business (Kim et al., 2019). The companies such as bank also get benefitted with the implementation of GHRM practices by engaging stakeholders, reducing the operating cost, increased quality of work (Venkatesh et al., 2023). To achieve the objectives of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), the organizations must shift their focus to Green which shall become a policy for every nation involving commitment from both the employees and the management (Wu et al., 2022). It is possible only when employees in the company are aware of GHRM-influenced activities and are encouraged to act in a green manner (DuBois and Dubois, 2012). In education institution also implementation of proper Green HRM system creates awareness leads to encourage waste management, reduction of unwanted resources, and maintaining the cleanliness of the campus which in turn gives satisfaction among various stakeholders. Thus, to improve overall productivity (Varma and Balachandran, 2021).

In India different PSUs such as BHEL, CIL, SAIL, NTPC etc. have adopted SDGs 12 for sustainability within their organizations (Basak, 2024). They have established and aligned both the business and environmental management objectives to reduce the negative effect on environment. Installation of green values and green culture at the organizational level may results to adoption of environmental friendly procedures in addition to knowledge capital preservation (Darvishmotivali and Altinay, 2022). In recent years, it has been noted that a majority of the organizations are identifying and promoting GHRM practices, which influence the environmental performance on a day to day basis (Tahir et al., 2024). Also, the Human Resource Management departments of the organizations are actively taking part to promote eco-friendly activities at the strategic level through awareness and implementation of policies and programmes and changing the behavior and attitude of the employees to make the organization more environment friendly.

Literature Review

Several studies exist to highlight the various dimensions concerning Green Human Resource Management. Milliman and Clair (1996) were reportedly first to make proposal on the significant role of human resource management with respect to environmental management. The term Green HRM was explained further where it was described as the incorporation program of environmental management within the system of HRM of a company (Renwick et al., 2008). However, the definition focuses on transforming workforce to transform into environmentally conscious workers with the purpose of accomplishing the organization's environmental goals and ultimately contributing to sustainability of environment (Opatha, 2016). It is an amalgamation of practices and policies that make employees work in favour of greening the organization which is advantageous to people, society, the environment, and business as a whole. It aims to lower the carbon emission at workplace through ensuring employee engagement and involvement employed within the organization all while cultivating a positive and healthy work atmosphere. The term green HRM consist of two key elements: firstly, it comprises of preservation of eco-friendly practices and the second one is the preservation of knowledge capital. It creates a sense of concern amongst the employees towards preservation of natural resources, contribute towards controlling pollution, waste management, interpretation of eco-friendly products or services within the organization (Mhetre & Sawant 2023). All HRM operations, includes Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development, Performance management and Appraisal, Rewards and Compensation and Employee empowerment and Participation should incorporate environmental considerations to make a green organization in real sense.

Green Recruitment and Selection has often been regarded as the significant aspects of GHRM. Mukherjee et al. (2020) explored the impact of paperless or digital hiring process on the environment. This process is design in a way that leads to less cost, time and energy during the process of recruiting applicants. There are some practices of green recruitment process such as online submissions and online posting of job applications, online telephonic interview or video conferencing etc. while recruiting. Job advertisements are based on environmental criteria with values and job descriptions that reflect sustainability agenda (Opatha, 2013). Similarly, green selection refers to the hiring of the skilled employees who are much aware and oriented to adopt change and fund the management of the environment (Tang et al., 2018). During the selection process, the candidates are asked questions relating to their environmental consciousness and awareness. As a result, the employees who are 'green oriented' are attracted, attained and to maintain sustainability of firms (Renwick et al., 2013). Thus, with proper green recruitment and

selection will motivate the individual to attract and retain them within the organization and leads to improve the performance of individuals (Elvina et al., 2024).

Green training and development are another significant dimension concerning of Green Human Resource Management. This refers to improving the skills and knowledge of workforce in relation to environmental management. In other words, it increases the value of employee's skill in order to motivate and retain employees. Now a days, firms are spending money and time to train employees by sharing skills and knowledge for solving issues relating to environment (Jabbour et al., 2010). Its goal is to raise environmental awareness to all employees of organization by offering training courses on environmental issues (North, 1997) and also to train employees to create environmental friendly workspace analyses (Renwick et al., 2012). Additionally, it involves creating programs to train staff to be more environmentally friendly, implementing job rotation to teach future green managers, and educating staff about green workplace practices (Jackson et al., 2011). It will assist employees to preserve energy, reduce the use of natural resources and get enhanced output (Jabbour, 2015). Moreover, different PSUs are also increasing the awareness level among employees regarding green training. However, the process starts with induction process where companies introduce the new recruiters to understand their duties towards environmental and responsibilities to fulfill the organizations environmental objectives by encouraging them to engaged in the green behavior of the organization (Revill, 2000). With the implementation of green training will enhance the employee's motivation which increases the efficiency of workers and thus it leads to improve the productivity in organization (Sharma and Dhamija, 2025).

Green Performance Management and Appraisal, another critical component of Green Human Resource Management, entails establishing green standards and assessing workers' performance towards environment. In other words, it involves setting of goals and targets in relation to environment for the workplace and evaluating employee performance in light of those objectives. It involves setting green aims, goals, and responsibilities to be taken into account while providing teams or employees with frequent feedback to assist them to meet the environmental targets or enhancing the environmental performances (Renwick et al., 2008; 2013). According to Mehta and Chugan (2015), green objectives and goals should be explicitly stated in the job description and in connection to the performance evaluation system. With proper green appraisal creates a positive and significant effect on green satisfaction in construction companies (Saputri et al., 2024). Thus, to assess employee's green performance appraisal, organizations should therefore establish environmental targets for each employee along with developing green criteria that are incorporated into the procedure and ensure them to complete

green performance feedback interview as an independent component of the performance feedback process (Opatha, 2013).

Once the Green performance management and Appraisal is done, the employees are to be rewarded and compensated in green terms. According to Opatha (2013), the system of Green Reward and Compensation addresses the procedures and policies needed to guarantee that employees' green performance is acknowledged with monetary rewards such as bonuses, incentives, cash as well as non-monetary incentives such as prizes, awards to encourage their environmental responsibilities (Renwick, 2008). In other words, it is intended to inspire workers to meet their environmental objectives and to apply innovative techniques to safeguard the environment by using limited resources. Rewards, which may be monetary or non-monetary, are tied to the success of managers. For easily inspiring motivating, competent, and talented people, managers link corporate goals with personal ones (Jackson et al., 2011). According to Bhushan and Mackenzie (1994), some businesses established environmental standards based on compensation reviews, while others established recognized incentives for exceptional environmental performance. It was also observed that awards based on recognition are provided when a candidate achieves the green goals in a very excellent manner. By rewarding and compensating employees for solving different environmental issues lead to the better performance of the organization (Ayana & Wodajo, 2024). Green compensation increases competitiveness and enthusiasm among employees which creates a positive and significant effect on green satisfaction in organization (Saputri et al., 2024). Additionally, it increases not only employee motivation, satisfaction but also increases the loyalty and productivity of the employees (Berber and Aleksic, 2016).

The Green Employee Participation and Empowerment are the significant elements of GHRM. The term incorporates, the involvement of workers on environmental social responsibility task such as taking part in green suggestion programs, creating environmental management training programs for union representatives, offering advice on how to resolve environmental problems, establishing green whistle blowing against misleading and collaborating with stakeholders on all environmental related matters (Renwick et al., 2013). The better employee-employer relation or relations with co-workers results to more productivity. Employees' active participation and empowerment help to take responsible decision towards environment management results to better green management. Green Employee Empowerment are gives authority to employees in decision-making process, thus to create a culture of trust and collaboration, and offering opportunities for skill development and career growth which contribute them towards better performance of organization (Sarfo et al, 2024). For every organization, it is vital for HR manager

to create an open working environment which will motivate the employees to share their ideas for further growth of organization.

Research Methodology

The present study aims to study the relationship between ‘Awareness’ and ‘Implementation’ of Green HRM in Mining industry in West Bengal. Following sub-sections present the methodological considerations for the present study:

Research Objectives

The objectives of the present research are as follows:

1. To examine the awareness of employees towards Green HRM in mining industry in West Bengal
2. To evaluate the implementation of Green HRM practices in mining industry in West Bengal
3. To identify relationship between awareness of employees towards Green HRM and implementation of Green HRM practices in mining industry

Methodology and Sample selection

The research entails to conducting the survey on gathering data from the participants in order to find out respondent's perspective on the current situation. Thus, it describes about descriptive research. The study has been conducted in a PSU under mining industry in West Bengal. The data collection process used both primary data source and secondary data source.

- a) **Primary Data source:** Collection of data by conducting survey through structured questionnaire distributed among different levels of employees in mining industry.
- b) **Secondary Data source:** Collection of data from research paper, Annual reports, Sustainability Reports, journals and website.

In the study, the snowball sampling technique is used to gathered data from the employees. For the sampling process, the targeted sample for the study is about 270 respondents. For that a well design questionnaires are distributed among 270 respondents for collection of data among the employees of the mining industry in West Bengal. Among them 243 questionnaires were completely filled by the employees and remaining 27 responses does not considered due to incomplete responses for study.

Measures: In this study, all actions are validated and items are adapted from past study. The questionnaire is distributed in two segments. First segment includes demographic questions such as age, marital status, gender, education, position and experience and the second segment of questionnaire comprises of awareness level and implementation of different GHRM practices includes Green Recruitment and selection, Green Training and development, Green Performance management and appraisal, Green Rewards and compensation, Green Employee participation and empowerment (Khaira, 2023). The variables were selected on the respected authors mentioned in their articles (Opatha & Hewapathirana, 2019; Renwick et al., 2012; Mandip, 2012; Ahmad, 2015; Shah, 2019). There were four questions on each of the green practice. The replies were evaluated using a five-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting "strongly disagree" and 5 denoting "strongly agree." To statistically analyze the gathered data, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences program "SPSS" version "30" was utilized.

Respondents' Demographic Characteristics

The case study examined the demographic details includes their age, gender, marital status, education, position and experience wise distribution of all respondents. Basically, this will make it easier to comprehend the general demographic profile of employees of mining industry in West Bengal.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of respondents / employees of mining industry

Variable	Classification	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male (M)	198	81.48%
	Female (F)	45	18.52%
Age-wise Distribution	21-30	29	11.93%
	31-40	126	51.85%
	41-50	56	23.05%
	51-60	32	13.17%
Marital Status	Married	166	68.31%
	Unmarried	77	31.69%
Educational Qualification	Doctorate	4	1.65%
	Post Graduate	97	39.92%
	Graduate	121	49.79%
	12 th	21	8.64%
Position wise Distribution	Top Level	13	5.35%
	Middle Level	105	43.21%
	Junior level	125	51.44%
Experience wise distribution	0-3 yrs	23	9.46%
	3-6 yrs	31	12.76%
	6-9 yrs	69	28.40%
	9 yrs-above	120	49.38%

Source: Author Survey, N (Number of Respondent) = 243

Table 1, indicates the respondents demographic characteristics in mining industry. First, Gender wise distribution of respondents shows that the majority of respondents are belongs to male category with 81.48% and rest belongs to female category with 18.52%. Secondly, the age wise distribution of respondents. The findings indicate that 51.85% of respondents are belongs to the age group 31 to 40 yrs which is considered as the major age group of respondents, 23.05% of respondents are belongs to age group 41 to 50 years, 13.17% of respondents are belongs to age group 51 to 60 years and 11.93% of respondent are belongs to age group 21 to 30 years. Thirdly, the respondent's marital status represents that 68.31% of respondents are married whereas only

31.69% of respondents are unmarried. Fourthly, the educational wise distribution of respondents indicates that majority of respondent i.e, 49.79% are Graduate. 39.92% of respondents are Post Graduate, 8.64% of respondents are 12th and only 1.65% of respondents are Doctorate. Fifth, the position wise distribution of respondents represents that majority of respondent, i.e, 51.44% belongs to junior level, 43.21% belongs to middle level and 5.35% of respondent belongs to top level. Finally, sixth, the experience wise distribution of respondents was done. It was found that 49.38% of respondents had 9 yrs and above experience. However, 28.40% of respondents had 6-9 yrs, 12.76% of respondents had 3-6 yrs and only 9.46% of respondents had less than 3 years of experience.

Result and Discussion

Testing of Reliability

Table 2. Reliability Statistics of respondents

Construct	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Awareness of employees towards Green HRM	8	.861
Implementation of Green HRM practices	20	.937

Source: Author Survey

The statistics use to measure the reliability is Cronbach alpha. This test is done to determine whether the questionnaire's design is reliable (Cronbach & Meehl, 1955) or not, and therefore this method is used to test the questionnaire's level of consistency. Thus, by using the Cronbach's Alpha technique the consistency of the aforementioned questionnaire is tested. Table 2 represents the alpha values of two constructs that were obtained from the data collected through the distributed questionnaires among respondents. The results indicate that Cronbach's alpha $\alpha = 0.861$ for 8 items deal with employees' awareness towards Green HRM in the organization as the first objective and Cronbach's alpha $\alpha = 0.937$ for 20 items deal with the implementation of Green HRM practices in the organization as the second objective. Table 2 depicts the reliability coefficient value of employee awareness towards green HRM and the implementation of green HRM practices of both eight and twenty items respectively that were included for the study.

Table 3. Cronbach's alpha for each Green HRM practice components

Constructs	Items Included	Cronbach's alpha	Internal Consistency
Green Recruitment and selection	4	.843	Good
Green Training and development	4	.785	Acceptable
Green Performance management and Appraisal	4	.806	Good
Green Rewards and compensation	4	.798	Acceptable
Green Employee participation and empowerment	4	.801	Good

Source: Survey, N (Number of Respondent) = 243

Table 3, represents the Cronbach alpha value of each construct which indicates the alpha value of each of the construct are above 0.70. The coefficient alpha should be equal or above 0.70 (DeVellis 2012) indicates about the instrument that is reliable for the study. In other words, it is possible to say that each construct's alpha values is greater than 0.7, thus those items created for each construct are legitimate and suitable for the study.

Analysis of 1st Objective: To find the Awareness of employees towards Green HRM in selected mining industry in West Bengal, the following scores were calculated:

Table 4: Operational Scale

Mean Value	Level of Awareness
Above 4 and till 5	High
Above 3 and less than 4	Moderate
Less than 3	Low

Source: Rawasdeha, 2018

The table 4 represents the operational scale. This scale is used to classify the data based on usage levels such as high, moderate and low with respect to mean score of 4 to 5 as high, mean score of 3 to 4 as moderate and mean score of below 3 consider as low category.

The statistical representation of data collected about employee's awareness towards Green HRM is as shown in Table 5. It depicts about the mean of each of the item and standard deviation of each of the item that were assessed through the questionnaire.

Table 5: Awareness of employees towards Green HRM with respect to its mean and standard deviation

No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank
1	The employee of the organization understands the concept of GHRM	4.05	.796	4
2	Green HR is at emerging stage in company	4.19	.766	2
3	The employees of the company planting trees within the premise	4.31	.698	1
4	The latest Power saving Appliance are used in organization	4.18	.750	3
5	Proper utilization of solar panel is considered as alternate source of energy	4.00	.787	5
6	Applying 3R's (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle) for Resources	3.44	.738	8
7	The Organization hold EMS Certification (ISO:14001)	3.92	.775	7
8	Paperless activity done by the employees in Organization	3.99	.730	6
Total mean score of awareness of employees towards Green HRM		4.01	0.755	

Source: Survey, N (Number of Respondent) = 243

From the table 5, the dataset indicated the overall mean score of awareness of employees towards green HRM was 4.01 with standard deviation of 0.755. The data interpret are as follows:

As per finding, the employees of the organization are planting trees regularly within the premise of the company. Both executive and non-executive employees were played an essential role in retaining green within the organization, with a mean score of 4.31, this factor achieved the top rank. However, the employees suggested about the initial stages of Green HR within the PSU, with a mean score of 4.19, this factor achieved 2nd rank. Latest powers saving appliances were also applying within the organization, with a mean score of 4.18, this factor achieved 3rd rank. The employees of the organization are sufficiently understood the concept of Green HR with 4th rank of mean score of 4.05. Their proper utilization of solar panel was using as alternate source of energy with mean score of 4.00, ranked 5th amongst eight Green practices. Most of the employees are doing paperless activity, prefer to do online work most with mean score of 3.99, with ranked 6th. Employees are aware of the certification of Environment management standards, EMS certification (ISO: 14001) with mean score of 3.92, ranked 7th. Within the premise of the company 3R's (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle) for resources are used as moderate level; however, it is least score amongst eight practices with mean score of 3.44. It shows all the employees both executive and non-executives have sufficient knowledge of greening concept. However, lack of knowledge is unable to deploy green policies in the organization. For

implementation of green policies, development of human resources may help to make reorientation of agenda, holding organizations accountable. Providing leadership on CSR while maintaining sustainability ensures to make the organization profitable and successful in future. Furthermore, it helps the decision makers to achieve organizational environmental goals (Garavan and McGuire 2010). The above results depicts about the employees awareness towards Green HRM. Hence, the first objective is accepted

Analysis of 2nd objective: Sequentially to evaluate the implementation of different Green HRM practices in mining industry in West Bengal, the respondents asked to rate the implementation of different Green practices are based on five-point Likert scale.

Both standard deviation and mean were used to analyze the study, by calculating each function or green practice that was evaluated based on the data achieved from the distributed questionnaire. Table 6 displays the mean scores for the implementation of green HRM practices.

Table 6. Implementation of Green HRM practices in mining industry, West Bengal

Sl. No.	Green HRM practices	Mean(M)	Standard deviation (SD)
i)	Green Recruitment and selection	3.605	.880
ii)	Green Training and development	3.773	.807
iii)	Green Performance management and appraisal	3.715	.857
iv)	Green Rewards and compensation	3.745	.848
v)	Green Employee participation and empowerment	3.698	.968
Total mean score and Standard deviation		3.707	.858

Source: Survey, N (Number of Respondent) = 243

The implementation of green HRM practices had an overall mean score of 3.707. It implies that the employees of the organization are adequately applying Green policies and practices in organization includes Green Recruitment and selection with mean score of 3.605, Green training and development with average score of 3.773, Green performance management and appraisal with mean score of 3.715, Green rewards and compensation have a mean score of 3.745, and Green employee participation and empowerment have a mean score of 3.698. In other words, it highlights the need to implement more Green training and developments as compared to other Green HRM practices within the PSU. Though Green HRM is at initial stage in India, in the

selected PSU under mining industry, the employees have sufficiently implemented few Green HRM practices confidently.

Analysis of 3rd Objective: To identify the relationship between awareness of employees towards green HRM and implementation of Green HRM practices in mining industry in West Bengal.

The correlation test designates the extent of the association between two constructs. The values of correlation analysis have to be within the range of -1 to +1. The values near +1 indicate that the two constructs are linked positively and the values near -1 show that the two constructs are linked adversely. If there is zero value, it indicates to have is no linkage in between the two constructs (Gogtay & Thatte, 2017). The correlation test values are shown in table 12:

Table 7. The Relationship between Two variables (Awareness of employees towards Green HRM and Implementation of Green HRM practices in mining industry, West Bengal)

Spearman rho Correlation	Variables		Awareness of employees towards Green HRM in mining industry	Implementation of Green HRM practices in mining industry
	Awareness of employees towards Green HRM in mining industry	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.849**
Sig. (2-tailed)			<0.001	
N		243	243	
Implementation of Green HRM practices in mining industry	Correlation coefficient	.849**	1.000	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001		
	N	243	243	

** Correlation coefficient is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

In this research to identify the two variables relationship, Spearman’s correlation method is used to compute the association among awareness of employees to Green HRM and implementation of Green HRM practices. Data represents the Spearman correlation value is 0.849, mentioned in table 7, between two variables that is awareness levels of employees towards Green HRM and implementation of Green HRM practice in mining industry in West Bengal. The study interprets that there is high and positive relation between the two variables. The above results of correlation show that the variables are positively correlated with each other because the values of these variables are positive. The values of correlation of all the relationships are at a higher level

because the values reported are more than 0.7. The results indicate that the correlation is at a higher level between the pair.

According to third objective, above findings says that the data is a statistically significant with p-value is less than 0.05 (i.e, $p < 0.001$). Thus, it shows to have positive impact between the awareness of employees towards Green HRM with implementation of Green HRM practices in mining industry, West Bengal is acceptable.

Awareness of GHRM with Sustainable Development Goals

It has been observed that in the selected PSU under mining industry, West Bengal, employees are much aware of several green HRM that are highly relates to the three SDG goals such as SDG 7, SDG 12 and SDG 15. As per the research indicates employees are planting trees within the premise of the organization to order achieve SDG 15 goals. Based on the indicators of Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation Sustainable Development Goals- National, 2023 report, there are several initiatives such as promoting renewable energy includes proper utilization of solar panel within organization helps to save energy, to implement proper power saving appliance in every organization results to less carbon emission in organization. It helps to maintain the ecosystem of the entire word which starts from particular organization. Employees are using power saving appliances such as using LED light to save energy; using renewable energy includes proper utilization of solar energy with the organization in order to achieve SDG 7. In this organization employees are need to more aware of 3R's (Reduce, Reuse and Recycle) of resources for reducing waste, efficient use of natural resources, reducing and recycling of waste material to order achieve the goals of Sustainable Development i.e., SDG 12 (Khajuria, 2020). Thus, the research states about the positive approach of GHRM to maintain sustainability within the organization by achieving SDG 7, SDG 12, and SDG 15.

Conclusion

From the above study, it suggested that the level of awareness of employees towards Green HRM is at its moderate to high level in mining sector in West Bengal. In India mining industry contribute a major role in Indian economic system. Therefore, the employees of the industry should be responsible towards protecting environment. Thus, employees should take initiatives to follow green practices not only at the work places but as well as at home. In the study most employees show positive responses towards awareness on Green HRM. It seems that employees are much aware of Green policies. The implementation level of Green HRM in the mining industry is also at its moderate level. Though it was found that Green HRM is at its initial stage

then also employees are trying to implement Green HRM practices positively in organization. Among all the Green HRM practices the implementation of Green training and development practices is at highest level in the mining industry. Finally, it also predicts there is positive and strong correlation between awareness of employees towards Green HRM with its implementation in mining industry in West Bengal. It depicts as long as the employees are more conscious towards Green, they will implement Greener HRM practices within organization from today to in future.

References

1. Ahmad, S. (2015). Green Human Resource Management: Policies and practices. *Cogent Business & Management*, 2(1).
2. Ansari, N.Y., Farrukh, M. & Raza, A. (2021). Green human resource management and employees pro-environmental behaviours: Examining the underlying mechanism. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(1), 229-238.
3. Arocena, P., Orcos, R., & Zouaghi, F. (2021). The impact of ISO 14001 on firm environmental and economic performance: The moderating role of size and environmental awareness. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(2), 955-967.
4. Ayana, I.D & Wodajo, M.G. (2024). Green Human Resource Management and Organizational Performance: Structural Equation Model Evidence from Nekemte Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Ethiopia. *International journal of management and Fuzzy systems*, 10(1), 1-16.
5. Azevedo, S. G., Carvalho, H., & Cruz Machado, V. (2011). The influence of green practices on supply chain performance: A case study approach. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 47(6), 850–871.
6. Barbier, E.B., & Burgess, J.C. (2017). The Sustainable Development Goals and the systems approach to sustainability. *Economics*, 11, 2017-28.
7. Basak, S. (2024), A Study on Linkages of Green HRM with SDG12 in Selected PSUs in India. *International Journal of Enhanced Research in Management & Computer Applications*, 13 (9), 17-24.

8. Berber, N. & Aleksic, M. (2016). Green Human Resource Management: Organizational Readiness for Sustainability. *International Scientific Conference the priority directions of national economy development*, 273-278.
 9. Bhushan, A.K., & Mackenzie, J.C. (1994), Environmental leadership plus total quality management equals continuous improvement, *Environmental TQM*, 2nd ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 72-93.
 10. Cronbach, L.J., & Meehl, P.E. (1955). Construct validity tests. *Psychological Bulletin*, 52(4), 281-302.
 11. Devellis, R.F.(2012). *Scale development Theory and Application* (3 ed.).
 12. Dubois, C.L.Z., & Dubois, D.A. (2012). Strategic HRM as social design for environmental sustainability in organization. *Human Resource Management*, 51(3), 799-826.
 13. Elvina, E., Saputra, A.R.P, Nuvriasari, A. (2024). Green training, Green recruitment and Green transformational leadership on employee performance in retail store. *International Journal of Management, Knowledge and Learning*, 1, 13-27.
 14. Garavan, T.N., & McGuire, D. (2010). Human Resource Development and Society: Human Resource Development's Role in Embedding Corporate Social Responsibility, Sustainability, and Ethics in Organizations. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 12(5).
 15. Gogtay, N.J., & Thatte, U.M. (2017). Principles of Correlation Analysis. *Journal of the Association of Physicians of India*, 65.
 16. Goswami, T.G. & Ranjan, S.K. (2015). Green HRM: Approach to sustainability in current scenario. *Journal for Studies in Management and Planning*, 1(4), 250-259.
 17. Jabbour, C.J.C., (2015). Environmental training and environmental management maturity of Brazilian companies with ISO14001: empirical evidence. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 96, 331-338.
 18. Jabbour, C.J.C., Santos, F.C.A., & Nagano, M.S. (2010). Contributions of HRM throughout the stages of environmental management: methodological triangulation applied to companies in brazil. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 21(7), 1049-1089.
-

19. Jackson, S. E., Renwick, D. W., Jabbour, C. J., & Muller-Camen, M. (2011). State-of-the-art and future directions for green human resource management: Introduction to the special issue. *German Journal of Human Resource Management*, 25(2), 99-116.
 20. Khajuria, A. (2020). Integrated Approach between DPSIR, Planetary Boundaries and Sustainable Development Goals towards 3Rs and Resource Efficiency. *World Environment*, 10(2), 52-56.
 21. Kim, Y.J., Kim, W.G., Choi, H.M. & Phetvaroon, k. (2019). The effect of green human resource management on hotel employees' eco-friendly behavior and environmental performance. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 76, 83–93.
 22. Lawn P. (2004). The sustainable development concept and indicators: an introductory essay. *International Journal of Environment and Sustainable Development*, 3(3-4), 199-234. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJESD.2004.005073>
 23. Mandip, G. (2012). Green HRM: People Management Commitment to Environmental Sustainability. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, 1. 244-252.
 24. Mehta, K., & Chugan, P.K. (2015). Green HRM in pursuit of environmentally sustainable business. *Universal Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 3, 74-81.
 25. Mhetre, D.D. & Sawant, S.B. (2023). A Study on Green HR practices adopted by Bharti Vidyapeeth management institute, Solapur Campus. *Bhairavi*, 22(02), 70-76.
 26. Milliman, J., & Clair, J. (1996). Best environmental HRM practices in the US. In W. Wehrmeyer (Ed.), *Greening people: Human resource and environmental management*. Sheffield, UK: Greenleaf Publishing.
 27. Mukherjee, S., Bhattacharjee, S., Paul, N., & Banerjee, U. (2020). Assessing Green Human Resource Management Practices in Higher Educational Institute. *Test engineering and management*, 82, 221 – 240.
 28. North, K. (1997), *Environmental Business Management – An Introduction*, 2nd ed, International Labour Office: Geneva.
 29. Opatha, H. H. D. N. P. (2013), *Green Human Resource Management: A Simplified Introduction*, HR Dialogue, Department of HRM, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, pp. 22-41.
-

30. Opatha, H. H. D. N. P., & Arulrajah, A. (2014), Green Human Resource Management: A Simplified General Reflections. *International Business Research*, 7(8)101-112.
 31. Opatha, H. H. D. N. P., & Hewapathirana, R.A. (2019). Defining Green and Green Human Resource Management: A Conceptual Study. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, 8(5), 1-10. Ramus, C. A. (2002). Encouraging innovative environmental actions: What companies and managers must do. *Journal of World Business*, 37, 151–164.
 32. Rawashdeha, A.M. (2018). The impact of green human resource management on organizational environmental performance in Jordanian health service organizations. *Management Science Letters*, 8, 1049- 1058.
 33. Raza, S.A. & Khan, K.A. (2022). Impact of green human resource practices on hotel environmental performance: the moderating effect of environmental knowledge and individual green values. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 34(6), 2154-2175. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-05-2021-0553>
 34. Renwick, D. (2008). Green HRM: A review, process model, and research agenda (Discussion Paper Series). The University of Sheffield.
 35. Renwick, D., Redman, T. & Maguire, S. (2012). Green human resource management: a review and research agenda. *International journal of management reviews*, 15 (1), 1-14.
 36. Renwick, D.W.S, Redman, T., & Maguire, S. (2013), Green Human Resource Management: A review and research agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 15(1), 1–14.
 37. Revill, C. (2000), The Greening of Personnel/Human Resource Management an Assessment, *International Journal of Applied HRM*, 3, 1-30.
 38. Saputri, I.S.A, Saputra, A.R.P, Susanto, D. (2024). The influence of Green compensation, Green appraisal and Green satisfaction on Employee performance in construction companies. *Journal of process management and new technologies*, 12(1-2).
 39. Sarfo, P.A., Zhang, J., Nyantakyi, G., Lassey, F.A., Bruce, E., Amankwah, O. (2024). Influence of Green Human Resource Management on firm’s environmental performance: Green Employee Empowerment as a mediating factor. *PLoS ONE*, 19(4): e0293957.
-

40. Shah, M. (2019). Green human resource management: Development of a valid measurement scale. *Business strategy and environment*, 1-15.
41. Sharma, D. & Dhamija, A. (2025). A study on the impact of green HRM and green training on environmental performance and green employee motivation and efficiency in education sector, *AiBi Revista de Investigación, Administración e Ingeniería*, 13(1), 75–81.
42. Tahir, A.H., Umer, M., Naumen, S., Abbass, K., & Song, H. (2024). Sustainable development goals and green human resource management: A comprehensive review of environmental performance. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 370, 122495.
43. Tang, G., Chen, Y., Jiang, Y., Paille, P., & Jia, J. (2018). Green human resource management practices: Scale development and validity. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resource*, 56, 31-55.
44. Venkatesh, A.N., Tirupude, R.R., Pathak, P., Pankajam, A., George, S., Adhav, S. (2023). Perception towards green human resource management Practices and implementation in financial institutions in Kerala. *World Journal of Management and Economics*, 98-108.
45. Verma, L. & Balachandran, V. (2021). Green human resource management practices-implementation in Universities and higher educational institutions - A study. *Sambodhi*, 44 (14), 93-98.
46. Wu, W., An, S., Wu, C.H., & Tsai, S.B. (2020). An empirical study on green environmental system certification affects financing cost of high energy consumption enterprises-taking metallurgical enterprises as an example. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 244:118848.